

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF TOURISM AND ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15621587>

Abstract. *This article provides directions for ensuring the stability of the tourism industry and the environment and contributing to their development, as well as suggestions and recommendations for the development of these areas.*

Keywords: *environment, tourism industry, sustainability, protection, eco-tourism.*

Tourism is a social, cultural and economic phenomenon which entails the movement of people to countries or places outside their usual environment for personal or business/professional purposes. These people are called visitors (which may be either tourists or excursionists; residents or non-residents) and tourism has to do with their activities, some of which imply tourism expenditure.

Using this definition, we can see that tourism is not just the movement of people for a number of purposes (whether business or pleasure), but the overall agglomeration of activities, services, and involved sectors that make up the unique tourist experience.

Tourism is travel for pleasure or business; also the theory and practice of touring, the business of attracting, accommodating, and entertaining tourists, and the business of operating tours. The World Tourism Organization defines tourism more generally, in terms which go "beyond the common perception of tourism as being limited to holiday activity only", as people "traveling to and staying in places outside their usual environment for not more than one consecutive year for leisure and not less than 24 hours, business and other purposes". Tourism can be domestic (within the traveller's own country) or international, and international tourism has both incoming and outgoing implications on a country's balance of payments.

Sustainable tourism is a concept that covers the complete tourism experience, including concern for economic, social and environmental issues as well as attention to improving tourists' experiences and addressing the needs of host communities. Sustainable tourism emerged as an outcome of preventing the uncontrolled and excessive use of mountain tourism resources and attractions in Sumadija and Western Serbia. Sustainable tourism should embrace concerns for environmental protection, social equity, and the quality of life, cultural diversity, and a dynamic, viable economy delivering jobs and prosperity for all.

Tourism is a dynamic and competitive industry that requires the ability to adapt constantly to customers' changing needs and desires, as the customer's satisfaction, safety and enjoyment are particularly the focus of tourism businesses.

TOURISM ENCOMPASSES:

Outbound Tourism: is what you may be most familiar with. It involves the people going from British Columbia to other provinces, territories or countries. For example, going to Hawaii for a holiday is considered outbound tourism. **Inbound Tourism:** The tourists coming to BC from other places are called inbound tourists. BC competes in a global market to attract tourists from the United States, Japan, Germany and many other countries. The industry also implements

marketing campaigns aimed at attracting travellers from other parts of Canada, as well as from within British Columbia.

Domestic Tourism: Approximately half of the tourists in BC each year are actually from within the province. BC Stats and Destination BC consider those travelling beyond their usual environment (typically more than 80 km from home) for business or for pleasure to be tourists.

Tourism is one of the fastest growing economies of the world. This does not only imply that economic growth is increasing, but also that more travellers demand a greater variety of destinations and attractions and that the experiences tourists are seeking are becoming diverse. In view of these changes sustainable development of tourism are becoming an increasingly complex matter to achieve.

Tourism is held to be sustainable to the extent tourism-specific planning and management systems take full account of current and future economic, social and environmental impacts. The interests of visitors, the industry, the environment and host communities should accordingly be balanced against each. Increasing differentiation, specialization and individualization of tourism practices (in part influenced by the information flow in social media) have made development trends less predictable and tourism more difficult to manage. Some destinations (nations, regions, places) have recently experienced unprecedented increases in the numbers of visitors, resulting in:

- 1) an increased pressure on nature resources and biodiversity;
- 2) reduced personal safety related to tourism activities and strenuous nature visitation;
- 3) conflicts of interests between actors who are involved in- or affected by tourism.

Tourism can be related to travel for leisure, business and visiting friends and relatives and can also include means of transportation related to tourism. This might be transportation to the general location as well as local transportation to and from accommodations, entertainment, recreation, nourishment and shopping. There is now

broad consensus that tourism should be sustainable. In fact, all forms of tourism have the potential to be sustainable if planned, developed and managed properly.

While "sustainable tourism" is a concept, the term "responsible tourism" refers to the behaviors and practices that can lead to sustainable tourism. All stakeholders are responsible for the kind of tourism they develop or engage in. Both service providers and purchasers or consumers are held accountable.

According to the Center for Responsible Tourism, responsible tourism is "tourism that maximizes the benefits to local communities, minimizes negative social or environmental impacts, and helps local people conserve fragile cultures and habitats or species. "Responsible tourism incorporates not only being responsible for interactions with the physical environment, but also of the economic and social interactions. While different groups will see responsibility in different ways, the shared understanding is that responsible tourism should entail improvements in tourism. This would include ethical thinking around what is "good" and "right" for local communities and the natural world, as well as for tourists. Responsible Tourism is an aspiration that can be realized in different ways in different originating markets and in the diverse destinations of the world.

When we are talking about environmental sustainability about tourism, we definitely include here ecotourism.

Ecotourism is broadly defined as low impact travel to endangered and often undisturbed locations. It is different from traditional tourism because it allows the traveler to become educated about the areas — both in terms of the physical landscape and cultural characteristics,

and often provides funds for conservation and benefits the economic development of places that are frequently impoverished.

Due to the growing popularity of environmentally-related and adventure travel, various types of trips are now being classified as ecotourism. Most of these are not truly ecotourism, however, because they do not emphasize conservation, education, low impact travel, and social and cultural participation in the locations being visited.

Therefore, to be considered ecotourism, a trip must meet the following principles set forth by the International Ecotourism Society:

- Minimize the impact of visiting the location (i.e.- the use of roads)
- Build respect and awareness for the environment and cultural practices
- Ensure that the tourism provides positive experiences for both the visitors and the hosts
- Provide direct financial aid for conservation
- Provide financial aid, empowerment and other benefits for local peoples
- Raise the traveler's awareness of the host country's political, environmental and social climate

Despite the popularity of ecotourism in the above-mentioned examples, there are several criticisms of ecotourism as well. The first of these is that there is no one definition of the term so it is difficult to know which trips are truly considered ecotourism.

In addition, the terms "nature," "low impact," "bio," and "green" tourism are often interchanged with "ecotourism," and these do not usually meet the principles defined by organizations like the Nature Conservancy or the International Ecotourism Society.

Critics of ecotourism also cite that increased tourism to sensitive areas or ecosystems without proper planning and management can actually harm the ecosystem and its species because the infrastructure needed to sustain tourism such as roads can contribute to environmental degradation.

Ecotourism is also said by critics to have a negative impact on local communities because the arrival of foreign visitors and wealth can shift political and economic conditions and sometimes make the area dependent on tourism as opposed to the domestic economic practices. Regardless of these criticisms though, ecotourism and tourism, in general, are increasing in popularity all over the globe and tourism plays a large role in many worldwide economies.

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